

Research Article

**Aspects of The Reproductive Biology and Natural Food and Feeding Habits of
Tilapia guineensis At The Tombia Mangrove Swamp Creek, Rivers State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

*The reproductive aspects and the food and feeding habits of *Tilapia guineensis* were investigated at the Tombia creek in the Nigeria, Niger Delta region. The fecundity of the fish, as well as the gonado-somatic index were examined. It was observed that total length range of fecund female fish was between 12.50 and 17.50cm, while the weight range fell between 35.70 – 113.20g. The weight of eggs ranged from 1.63-5.00g while the number of oocyte ranged between 121 – 1,052. The GSI ranged from 2.66 – 11.19. The results indicated that fecundity increases with age or size of fish. The food and feeding habits of the fish showed in all the size range that green algae are the most dominant food organisms in the creek. This was followed by cyanobacteria, detritus and insect larvae, using the numerical abundance method (NAM), and the Frequency of Occurrence Method (FOM). *T. guineensis* of the Tombia creek, is thus unspecialized feeder or an omnivore feeding on what is readily available in the environment.*

KEY WORDS: Fecundity, gonado-somatic index, natural food, feeding habit, *Tilapia guineensis*, Tombia Creek.

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Introduction

Tilapia inhabits a variety of fresh and brackish water habitats, from shallow streams and ponds through the rivers, lakes and estuaries. They are hardy species produced through several culture methods under a wide range of environmental conditions.

Tilapia is both a genus of fishes in the cichlidae family and the common name for nearly a hundred species of fresh water and some brackish water cichlid fishes belonging to the

three genera *Tilapia*, *Sarotherodon* and *Oreochromis* (El-Sayed *et al* 2007). Although tilapia is a native to Africa and the Middle East, most of all farmed tilapia is grown outside its native habitat.

Tilapia are plastic animals because their growth and maximum obtainable size can be seriously influenced by the physical and biological composition of their environment.

Tilapia guineensis is a euryhaline species found along the West African Coast-line Interest in this fish is increasing, especially in areas of high and variable salinities, which characterize the estuaries and extensive lagoons in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Studies of inland water systems in the Niger Delta have focused on major rivers with little attention to the creeks and estuaries, despite their abundance and importance in the region. (Onyieche and Akankali 2013).

In the design of fisheries management, information on reproduction is very vital (Njiru *et al* 2006). This work therefore considered some aspects of the reproductive biology of the *Tilapia guineensis*.

Several workers have different views on fecundity and its estimation. Bagenal (1978) defined fecundity as the number of ripening eggs found in the female just prior to spawning. This is where the species have a well-defined breeding season. This being the number of eggs produced by a female per year (being the period between the start of one breeding season and the start of the next). Bone *et al* (1995) observed that fecundity increases with age. Also two important data input in fisheries management are morphometric characteristics and spawning pattern (Oribhabor and Adisa-Bolanta 2009).

Studies have been carried out in various aspects of the biology of important cichlids of commercial value by Fryer and Iles (1972), Babiker and Ibrahim (1979), Stewart (1988), Admassu (1996), Fawole and Arawomo (2000), El-Sayed *et al* (2007), Oribhabor and Adisa-Bolanta (2009), Bob-Manuel *et al* (2016).

Stomach content of a fish varies with the time of the day, size of the fish and the season of the year. The health and growth of a fish will depend on what and how it feeds (Pius and Benedicta 2002).

A knowledge on the natural food of fish and its feeding is an important part of aquaculture development. It suggest to fish farmers the type as well as the quantity of local supplementary feed to use. It is also important to know other animals in its habitat in order to be aware of its nutritional needs and interaction with other organisms. Therefore

studies to evaluate the stomach content try to identify and quantify the resource that a fish species uses, providing information on those selected from the choice available in the environment. Such studies could also yield information needed in the management of the riverine Tilapia which is a very useful food fish for the riverine community.

Various investigations have been conducted into stomach content of Tilapia species with the aim of determining their dietary requirements. These include; Fagade and Olaniyan (1973), who observed the principal food items of tilapia species as algal filaments, diatoms and unidentified organic matter. Nwafili and Lamai (2003) reported that ile tilapia feed mainly on phytoplankton or benthic algae; Komolafe and Arawomo (1998) worked on the distribution and feeding habit of *O. niloticus* in Opa reservoir Ile-Ife; Arawomo and Fawole (1997) assessed the food and feeding habits of *Sarotherodon galilaeus* in Opa reservoir Ile-Ife; Pius and Benedicta (2002) noted that *O. niloticus* ingest a wide range of food organisms in their environment. The food for *S. melanotheron* was reported as insect larvae, plant matter, plankton, blue-green algae, and sand grains (Ofori-Danson and Grace, 2005).

Fagade (1971) observed at the Lagos lagoon that they fed on algae, detritus, sand grains and invertebrates. Agbabiaka (2012) noted the food preference for *T. zilli* in River Otamiri as algae, vegetative matter, detritus, and aquatic invertebrate larvae. Other studies are Nile Tilapia at Ero reservoir in Ekiti (Osho *et al*, 2006); Agbabiaka (2010); *S. melanotheron* (Ofori - Danson and Grace, 2005) in Ghana. The dormant food organisms in order of importance in the Tilapia species of River Sombreiro were higher plant parts, and detritus, blue-green algae, filamentous and green algae and a mixture of unicellular desmids (Nwadiaro, 1984). Fagade (1978) also reported that Tilapia species are omnivorous feeding on what is readily available in the environment either plant or animal source.

This work is thus a continuous effort at investigating the biology of these brackish water tilapia which are important fish food to the people, with a view to establishing a proper fisheries management strategy as well as providing baseline information on *Tilapia guineensis* at the Tombia Creek in the Niger Delta.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The Tombia creek is located north of Rumuolumeni and Ogbakiri towns and is one of the tributaries of the New Calabar River. It is in the Degema Local Government Area of Rivers State and Southeast of the Niger Delta between latitude 4°31'N and 4°59'N and longitude 6°47'E and 6°59'E (Fig. 1 & 2).

Fig. 1 Map Showing the Niger Delta Region with the Tombia Creek

Fig. 2: Map Showing the Tombia Creek

Sampling Procedure

Samples of fish were collected between February and April 2016 from artisanal fisher men. A total of three hundred and fifty (350) specimens were collected. The fishing gear used were mainly cast nets. Samples collected were immediately taken to the laboratory in an ice chest.

In the laboratory total length and standard length were taken with a measuring board and recorded to the nearest 0.1cm. The total weights (TW) of the fish was also taken to the nearest 0.1g using an electronic top load weighing balance (Model xy 500 cy). The fish specimens were dissected individually, the gut content removed and emptied into a petri dish for analysis of food items. The gut contents were analysed individually by using the numerical and frequency of occurrence methods (Hyslop, 1980, Ugwumba, 1988).

The stomach contents were observed using a binoculars microscope.

Numerical abundance method (NAM) = $\frac{\text{Total no. of particular food items} \times 100}{\text{Total no. of all food items}}$ 1

Frequency of occurrence method (FOM) = $\frac{\text{Total no. of stomachs with particular food items} \times 100}{\text{Total no. of stomach with food}}$ 1

The fish were sorted out into total length range as follows 9.00 - 13.50cm; 13.51-17.50cm; 17.51-20cm. The key to the identification of food organisms was obtained from Hynes (1950), Ugwumba and Ugwumba (2007).

Fecundity Estimation

Thirty one (31) female fish specimens were observed to contain oocytes (immature eggs) out of the 350.

During the dissection of the fish to bring out the gut, the ovaries of fish containing eggs were also removed and present in 4 percent formalin in specimen bottles. For the estimation of fecundity the ovary containing the eggs was emptied into a wash glass, the formalin washed off with water and the eggs separated from the ovarian tissues that bind them together. This was further washed and placed on a filter paper to remove excess moisture and then spread out in an oven for 5 minutes at a temperature of 37°C for drying. The whole egg sample was weighed, then a subsample of about 50 oocyte was taken. The weight of this subsample was determined. By a simple proportion the number of oocytes (immature eggs) in the ovary can be estimated from the weight of the subsample (Bagenal, 1978).

Gonado-Somatic Index (GSI) was determined for the fecund fish according to Imevbore (1970) as;

$$\text{GSI} = \frac{\text{Weight of ovary} \times 100}{\text{Total Weight of fish.}}$$

Results

Table 1: Morphometric characteristics of fecund female *T. guineensis*

Morphometric Parameters

Total length range of fecund females (cm)	12.50-17.50
Standard length range of fecund females (cm)	9.50-14.00
Weight range of fecund females (g)	35.70-113.20
Weight range of eggs of fecund females (g)	1.63-5.00
Fecundity range of females (eggs)	121-1052
Gonado-somatic index (G.S.I) range.	2.66-11.19

Table 2 Analysis of food items found in *Tilapia guineensis* in the Tombia Creek. Rivers State - Nigeria using the numerical abundance method (NAM).

Food items	Total Length Range cm			Numerical Abundance Method		
	9.00-13.50	13.51-17.50	17.51-20.00	9.00-13.50	13.51-17.50	17.51-20.00
Green algal filaments	7332	5511	200	46.50	36.40	23.70
Fragments of Aquatic hydrophytes	47	76	28	0.30	0.50	3.32
Plant seeds	26	18	10	0.16	0.12	1.18
Crustacean appendages	53	80	16	0.34	0.53	1.90
Unidentified plant parts	62	46	14	0.39	0.30	1.66
Cyanobacteria	2515	2005	80	15.95	13.24	9.48
Hymenoptera nymph	25	566	12	0.16	3.74	1.42
Detritus	3,000	1450	94	19.03	9.58	11.14
Insect larvae	2508	1525	76	15.91	10.07	9.00
Fish scales	12	20	17	0.08	0.13	2.01
Diatoms	31	1800	110	0.20	11.89	13.03
Copepods	46	1960	125	0.29	12.94	14.81
Sand grains	94	54	12	0.60	0.36	1.42
Fish eggs	16	30	50	0.10	0.20	5.92
Total number of stomach examined	192	143	15	192	143	15
Number of empty stomachs	3	2	-	3	2	-
Total no. of all food items.	15,767	15,141	844			

Table 3 Analysis of food items found in *Tilapia guineensis* using the Frequency of Occurrence Method (FOM) in the Tombia Creek. Rivers State - Nigeria.

Food items	Total Length Range cm			Frequency of Occurrence Method		
	9.00-13.50	13.51-17.50	17.51-20.00	9.00-13.50	13.51-17.50	17.51-20.00
Green algal filaments	82	63	10	42.71	44.06	66.67
Fragments of Aquatic hydrophytes	10	43	6	5.21	30.07	40.00
Plant seeds	4	15	5	2.08	10.49	33.33
Crustacean appendages	5	6	12	2.60	4.20	80.00
Unidentified plant parts	14	21	9	7.29	14.69	60.0
Cyanobacteria	33	10	7	17.18	6.99	66.67
Hymenoptera nymph	24	50	3	12.50	34.97	20.00
Detritus	38	18	10	19.79	12.59	66.67
Insect larvae	33	41	09	17.19	28.67	60.00
Fish scales	4	56	08	2.08	39.16	53.33
Diatoms	18	32	06	9.38	22.38	40.00
Copepods	12	28	07	6.25	19.58	46.67
Sand grains	09	15	09	4.69	10.49	60.00
Fish eggs	3	12	12	1.56	8.39	80.00
Total number of stomach with foods	192	143	15	192	143	15
Number of empty stomachs	3	2	-	3	2	-

Results and Discussion

The morphometric characteristics of the fecund females of *T. guineensis* at the Tombia Creek showed that only female fish, between the total length of 12.50cm and length of 9.50cm start the production of oocyte from their ovary. This is supported by the work of Bone *et al* (1995) that fecundity increases with age or size. The weight range of fecund females was also between 35.70 and 113.20g. This is an indication that female fish of smaller size (weight) did not commence egg production. The range of G.S.I. was also between 2.66 and 11.19 (Table 1).

The analysis of the food items found in the stomach of *T. guineensis* indicated that in all the size groups, green filamentous algae was the most dominant food item. This was followed by detritus, cyanobacteria and insect larvae in that order. (Table 2 and 3). These findings are similar to those of Fagade (1971, 1978) at the Lagos and Lekki lagoons respectively; Nwadiaro (1984) at the Sombreiro River; Agbabiaka (2010, 2012) at River Otamiri. From the numerical abundance method it was observed that as the fish increased in size, green algal filaments which was most dominant at the younger stage, reduced in importance from 46.50% to 23.70% from TL. Range of 9.00-13.50cm and 17.51-20.00cm respectively. However, contrary to the observation of Fagade (1971) who reported that in the *T. melanotheron* of Lagos Lagoon sand grains and unidentified food formed 73% of the stomach content; in the *T. guineensis* of Tombia creek, these food items are of less importance. It was also reported that 21.6% of *T. guineensis* in Lagos Lagoon (Fagade 1971) had empty stomachs contrary to the findings in this work where only 1.43% of the fish had empty stomachs. This is indicative of the availability of much food items in the creeks of the Niger Delta during the sampling period. The *T. guineensis* of Tombia creek are opportunistic and omnivorous, feeding on available food items in the environment either plants or animal materials.

Conclusion

The *T. guineensis* of Tombia creek is highly fecund exhibiting reproductive characteristics at a length range of between 12.50 - 17.50cm and weight of between 35.70 - 113.2g among the females is indicative of the fact that reproduction started at an early age. The food and feeding habits showed the fish as an omnivore that fed on what is readily available in the aquatic ecosystem.

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